

APPLICATION OF FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTERNET MARKETING IN UKRAINE

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Abstract: The Internet age has created a system of media options used in marketing, and theoretical studies of the digital space have expectedly moved to the applied plane. The purpose of the academic paper is to establish the effectiveness of introducing the training course on studying foreign experience in Internet marketing and using it to the Ukrainian practice of advertising and professional education. The scientific work is also aimed at defining and describing new options for the development of foreign Internet marketing, assessing students the introduction of a new course on understanding new foreign options of media operating in the digital plane. The complexity of approaches distinguishes the methodology of the academic paper. The method of the pedagogical experiment is the basic one in the research; the descriptive method, synthesis and analysis have been used to describe and analyze the theoretical material; the statistical methods have been applied to conduct surveys of respondents. The research result is the effectiveness and improvement of the quality of education due to introducing a new training course on studying foreign experience in Internet marketing, considering correlations between traditional advertising and digital marketing, and the Internet industry.

In prospect, it is expedient to introduce new educational disciplines on the history of the development of digital marketing and investigate new media options used abroad and in practice in Ukraine.

Keywords: AdSense, AdWords, console, digital communication, digitalization of education, technology effectiveness, Google Analytics, Google Search, Pay Per Click, SEO, the transformation of the educational process.

1 Introduction

A great variety of enterprises and large companies in Ukraine use digital marketing to obtain a specific advantage. Social media is spreading rapidly throughout the world, forasmuch as the media on the Internet, digital marketing is used to gain competitive benefits. Social media is also viral among professional marketing specialists. After all, the Internet, social networks, and digital platforms make it possible to communicate and exchange publications.

The development of Internet technologies, followed by the development of digital communication tools, has stimulated entrepreneurs to change the ways of transmitting information about products and services (Selin, et al., 2016).

From such standpoints, the issue of developing information technologies is considered in modern marketing, updating the communication strategy within the limits of digital marketing. The strategy of using Internet marketing tools is a variable component; it is expedient to examine this issue constantly, to master new applications, new tools and operating systems (Ransbotham and Mitra, 2009; Nenthien, Loima, 2016). That is why scientific studies in the field of marketing and a comprehensive approach to the means of informing and advertising goods and services remain relevant.

Recently, in foreign marketing, a lot of attention has been paid to start-ups and enterprises ready to actively implement digital marketing as a condition for a successful business strategy to use the full potential of online marketing in competitive conditions (Kannan, 2017). Internet marketing can also be considered the practice of using web channels to spread information about products and services, and the company brand among the target audience.

It should be noted that the primary goal of online marketing activities is to prompt as many potential customers as possible to visit a particular website, which can be turned into paid ones, and the business into a profitable one. Accordingly, the accompanying goals of Internet marketing are activities on increasing brand recognition, conducting effective advertising campaigns, determining pricing policy and forming marketing offers (discounts, promotions, customer loyalty programs).

By the way, Internet marketing media usually include Website/Blog, Social Media Marketing, Email Marketing, Search Engine Marketing, Content Marketing, Video Blogging, and Online Classifieds.

2 Literature Review

Introducing the foreign experience of Internet marketing into practical activities and professional education is relevant to modern marketing. The use of marketing tools, the search for effective ways to expand the audience of consumers and the communication circle of potential buyers, and the use of digital technologies in educational practice are carried out (Alfarwan, 2019). The researchers in the pedagogical field studied the methods of introducing foreign experience in Internet marketing from an educational and methodological standpoint. They considered learning processes in higher education institutions using innovative technologies based on current materials and experience (Farkas, 2012; Boghian, 2019).

In several studies, the task of classifying a reasonably wide, diverse and systemic activity of Internet marketing in a broad context has been implemented, namely: strategies for managing communication with customers (Hwang, 2009); mechanisms of electronic markets (Novak and Schwabe, 2009); features of working at online auctions (Loebbecke et al., 2010); challenges and prospects for the development of e-branding (Grover, 2010), which have also been considered in conjunction with the unique IB challenges, taking into account website evaluation algorithms (Chiou et al., 2010); piracy and countermeasures in the digital space and security (Smith and Telang, 2009); prospects for the development of technological architecture (Du et al., 2008).

The digitization of the educational space is also the subject of scientific study (Henderson, et al., 2017; Shulman, 2018; Xiangjun, Yip, 2018). Experimental data on the problems of digitization in higher education were published; the study was conducted with the involvement of students of technical and natural sciences (Nenthien, and Loima, 2016).

Educational technologies related to investigating modern high-tech bulk equipment laws and actions have been studied for the past several decades. Their use has fundamentally changed not only the forms of higher economic education but also the philosophy of education has been revised (Howlett, Waemusa, 2019). A separate topic in pedagogy is the consideration of the transition from methods and forms of traditional teaching to education in the digital technology space. This primarily describes and develops complex models of training specialists in university education (Sereda, 2014; Dizon, 2018).

The problematic field of choosing Internet marketing training methods of effectively incorporating foreign experience into domestic practice is a broad issue. The scholars point to the lack

of sufficient material and technical opportunities for using online marketing tools as much as possible in professional activities, particularly due to the lack of opportunities to get acquainted with them during the training period (Shulman, 2018). And this is a serious and great obstacle, which should be eliminated by practicing teachers with the support and assistance of the administrations of educational institutions. The studies carried out in this direction have confirmed the thesis that the high costs of equipment and training in Internet marketing, and the involvement of leading specialists in this field in this process, are necessary for training qualified marketing specialists (Selin, et al., 2016).

In several studies on the regional features of implementing Internet marketing, the specifics of the work of entrepreneurs in the market have been established. For instance, working with marketing technology in Canada also involves several proprietary Internet products. As an example, working with the appropriate choice of keywords, led by the work of TRS Tech, which offers the best digital marketing services in Toronto, is one of the market-leading technologies in Canada (Corley, Jourdan, Ingram, 2013).

Internet marketing, in the interpretations of various researchers from different countries, provides an opportunity to actively engage in attracting the audience's attention with high-tech and practical tools; moreover, it is also a wide field of the global educational environment.

3 Aims

The present research aims to establish the effectiveness of introducing the training course on studying foreign experience into the Ukrainian practice of advertising and professional education. The research purpose determines the solution to several research objectives, namely:

- to establish the components of Internet marketing systems;
- to determine the relevance evaluation of the set of high-tech means and training tools used by the respondents during training;
- to estimate material costs and unique skills of the central thematic blocks of the discipline;
- to reveal the advantages and the disadvantages of working with foreign experience in Internet marketing in the framework of the educational course.

4 Materials and Methods

The research group has used a set of methods to conduct an effective study. A comprehensive approach to the research makes it possible to use the descriptive method for analyzing theoretical and methodological issues. Statistical methods provide an opportunity to collect the necessary materials, conduct monitoring activities, and measure the experiment's results (pre-experimental and post-experimental evaluation phases). Statistical methods have also been used to evaluate the results of the experiment.

Sixty-five students were involved in the research who expressed a desire to participate in the study of the project group on examining foreign experience in Internet marketing. The training course was introduced for students of the 3rd year (first) bachelor's level of education of the mechanical and mathematical faculty, specialty 07 "Management and administration" of the Mykolaiv National University named after V. O. Sukhomlynsky, Ukraine.

The method of the pedagogical experiment was applied during the 2021-2022 academic year (one academic semester). The experimental method was used to determine the level of significance and importance of students' motives to study new technologies in marketing, and the prospects for introducing foreign experience into practice. It also investigated the effectiveness of teaching the course on Internet marketing for training professionals in the economic sphere.

Stage 1. In the first stage, a preliminary survey was conducted on the respondents' attitudes to Internet marketing and updating the discipline based on foreign experience. Preparation of educational and methodological materials, and technical and advisory base was carried out. The selected educational and practical materials for the courses have been prepared, as well as specialized tools and software. Additionally, preliminary training was conducted with technical specialists who will help in practical and laboratory classes; they will lead and accompany such courses. Moreover, laboratories and instructions for independent work were also prepared.

Experimental studies were based on introducing a set of educational materials specially developed by the research group. The content of the course uses the capabilities of marketing tools, social networks, mobile applications, advertising software, etc.

Stage 2. At this stage, in parallel, active training was conducted within the course, and a preliminary survey was carried out to assess the relevance of the complex of high-tech means and training tools used by the respondents. The assessment by students of material costs and unique skills of the main thematic blocks of the academic discipline was also established.

Stage 3. At the final stage, a final survey was conducted among the respondents regarding the relevance evaluation of a set of high-tech tools, and training tools in studying Internet marketing. At the same time, the respondents were surveyed regarding the advantages and disadvantages connected with the introduction of foreign experience in Internet marketing in training. The purpose of the survey is to establish possible progressive changes in the awareness and relevance of Internet marketing knowledge in the study groups participating in the experiment.

The third stage also involved summing up, analyzing the results obtained during the experiment. By the way, changes related to thematic and content modifications in the curriculum and the readiness degree of all participants in the educational process towards changes and the transition to new disciplines in the training process were measured.

Surveys and questionnaires were conducted among respondents voluntarily. The experiment was conducted in agreement with the administration. The students signed the consent to participate in the experiment.

The research group and the teaching staff adhered to the ethical principles throughout the experiment. The data obtained during the research were anonymous and private. The principles of cooperation and integrity were followed during the preparation of the tests.

The research was observational and did not involve non-invasive interventions. The researchers did not apply actions that would affect the frankness and truthfulness of the participants' answers and decisions.

There were several difficulties and problem positions of the research that arose during the experiment, namely: significant time costs (1 semester - 6 months); it is also not possible to determine the reasons for the change in the respondents' evaluations; there are no opportunities to conduct a qualitative in-depth study.

5 Results

Foreign experience in the formation and implementation of Internet technologies and the communication complex of marketing in the educational process in Ukraine is an essential basis for the high-quality training of a specialist in the field of management and advertising.

At the first preparatory stage, the project group consulted with the experiment participants, scientific and pedagogical workers and technicians from the support service.

Knowledge in Internet marketing field will help inform the public about one’s own business and identify such a company among other competitive ones. It was also necessary to identify the main thematic blocks of the discipline and consider the leading components of Internet marketing, determine their importance, and prepare educational and methodological materials, and software products (Figure 1).

Source: Author’s development

Internet marketing is applied in advertising and marketing activities; the use of e-mail and Internet resources to stimulate sales is also provided. E-commerce of this type also involves the promotion of direct sales through digitalization as an additional position to selling the product from websites. Internet marketing is a tool for attracting potential customers’ attention to goods and services using digital tools (video, audio, flash animation, images, etc.). Marketing actions should be a planned, well-designed and organized temptation to choose at the expense of the advertised object, or services that a particular website, profile, or group offer. Such advertising information is placed on the website’s main pages to reach the target audience.

Internet marketing has many means of obtaining traffic for marketing activities; the attention is primarily paid to Search Engine Optimization (SEO). This term defines the digital marketing category, ways to find a good place for a website in search engine results based on keywords and phrases. Priority in such a search is given to keywords. The largest and most popular systems include Google, Baidu, Yahoo, and Bing. Along with this, it is essential to consider the availability of a web page that is easy to find, categorize and analyze. The algorithm for creating a successful web page is one of the basics of training a qualified specialist. Among the digital marketing tools, SEO is a

valuable and important component, without which it is impossible to organize a successful marketing campaign.

At the second stage, classes on the educational discipline of “Internet marketing. Foreign experience” was actively conducted. The respondents were also asked to highlight topics introducing marketing tools that should be included in the educational process. The list contained components of Internet marketing that the teachers suggested, and the respondents were asked to add their own ones. The results are represented in percentages (Table 1).

Tab. 1: The relevance evaluation of the complex of high-tech means and training tools used by the respondents (prior to the start of the experiment)

Number of respondents	Digital technologies
72%	Website/Blog
65%	Social Media Marketing,
68%	Video Blogging
54%	Online Classifieds.
62%	E-mail Marketing
65%	Search Engine Marketing
70%	Content Marketing

Source: Author’s development

The survey showed that the respondents supported a comprehensive approach to Internet marketing. This is confirmed by the absence of significant differences in the importance assessment of each topic. This has dictated to the research group the direction on the mandatory use of the entire set of educational issues within the new discipline. The most excellent preference was given to the need to possess knowledge of creating and maintaining websites and blogs (72%), video blogging (68%), as well as work with content marketing (70%).

Students passed the preliminary test and gave the first assessments for the new academic discipline. The respondents were asked to choose those topics that required modern and valuable technical means and special skills.

The analysis of the research group’s answers was aimed at helping to understand the informal and material aspects of implementing the educational goals to establish the professional specificity and priorities of implementing educational programs. Such an approach will help the administration to plan material resources for educational equipment, improve the professional level, and facilitate orientation to foreign experience and innovations. The proposed topics had to be evaluated on a 10-point scale; each topic was scored separately from 1 to 10. The highest results are presented in the graph 1.

Graph 1: Evaluation of material costs and special skills of the main thematic blocks of the discipline “Internet marketing: foreign experience.”

Source: Author’s development

The survey results show that blogging, creating websites, video blogging require the most preparation and material effort – from 7 points to 10. Content marketing and Search Engine Marketing

were also costly for respondents (cost – 5 points, special skills – 6 points out of 10). The general interest and the ability to navigate in the difficult moments of studying Internet marketing testify to the awareness of future specialists and the

need to introduce a course on Internet marketing.

In the III stage, in parallel with the training of students on the course, a survey of respondents was conducted regarding the creation of a rating of advantages and disadvantages revealed while studying the new academic discipline "Internet marketing: foreign experience" at a higher educational institution. From the list of educational topics proposed by the research group, it was necessary to choose from the most important to the least important among the advantages and disadvantages of working within marketing technologies (Table 2).

Tab. 2: Advantages and difficulties in working with foreign experience in Internet marketing in the framework of the educational course

Advantages	Disadvantages
<p>1. It is possible to introduce online courses, distance forms of education and communication between students and teachers; it is convenient; moreover, it is not regulated by distance communication channels.</p> <p>2. Under challenging moments, essential topics can be relearned, and the acquired knowledge can be consolidated in practice.</p> <p>3. Increasing the level of digital literacy among teachers and students.</p> <p>4. Acquisition of a range of modern practical skills in Internet marketing.</p> <p>5. Expanding the circle of knowledge about innovations and successful foreign experience for a specialist in advertising.</p>	<p>1. A large educational load concerning the digitalization program's creation, implementation and maintenance.</p> <p>2. Insufficient modern and powerful technical outfit, and equipment of educational institutions.</p> <p>3. In real practice, the infrastructure has low bandwidth, outdated software, and technical means.</p> <p>4. The high cost of designing in the space of high technologies.</p> <p>5. Inconsistency in the content of educational programs and students' needs; outdated educational design of courses.</p>

Source: Author's development

A significant advantage of familiarization with innovations in Internet marketing is the attraction of discoveries and useful findings of foreign specialists, creating opportunities for distance and online education and practical activities. Also, among the positive moments, the respondents have noted a new type of communication between the teacher, advertising practitioner and student. Within the limits of new languages and a new discipline, students can master complex topics; by the way, their multiple reviewing and additional practical classes and dialogue with the audience are also possible.

Finally, the necessity of studying marketing means and high-tech tools (at the end of the experiment) has also been reviewed.

Tab. 3: Evaluation of the relevance of the complex of high-tech means and training tools used by the respondents

Number of respondents	Digital technologies
80%	Website/Blog
70%	Social Media Marketing,
68%	Video Blogging
64%	Online Classifieds
68%	Email Marketing
73%	Search Engine Marketing
74%	Content Marketing

Source: Author's development

In general, it is clear from the survey results that the respondents have positively evaluated the practice of studying foreign experience in implementing and mastering new components of

Internet marketing. In general, the number of students who have highly assessed the study of foreign experience in using new technologies and software in marketing activities increased by 9%. This presupposes their mandatory use in educational activities.

6 Discussion

The number of studies and practical cases related to Internet marketing has been steadily increasing since the very beginning of the Internet and the discovery of its new possibilities. Constant monitoring of foreign experience related to marketing issues and innovations will help to identify valuable innovations in this field; it will provide an opportunity to improve training courses constantly. Corley, Jourdan, Ingram, (2013) investigated in their study the research activity of scientists at the level of the volume of scientific publications on Internet marketing; they have noted that the number of such investigations is growing. They studied the five most popular marketing journals. They revealed that the best source for exploring foreign experience in marketing is Marketing Science – 72,7% of publications are published on this topic. Along with this, foreign studies in marketing journals are also popular ("Formal Theory / Lit Review" (45,5%), "Field Study – Secondary" (27,3%) and "Field Study – Primary" (18,2%)). This means that Internet marketing is gradually gaining popularity. However, there are prospects for further work on this issue. Our research team has also established that students understand the relevance and necessity of learning about Internet marketing innovations. Therefore, the assessment of the relevance of studying the work of various marketing applications and tools in the Internet space showed that the understanding of the importance of taking into account foreign experience and innovations in teaching Internet marketing increased by a total of 9%.

An essential component of Internet marketing is studying national features of advertising activities and innovations in the introduction of marketing tools in the digital space in modern education (Boyd, 2014; AmCham, 2021). A similar study on the features of introducing Internet marketing was conducted in India (Umamaheswari, Kumawat, 2020). The study aimed to highlight foreign innovations in online marketing, the emergence and use of new media options. It has been proven that Indian companies are interested in innovations to obtain competitive advantages. The authors believe that the constant interest in innovations in digital marketing and the Internet industry primarily helps start-ups and small businesses to carry out business planning successfully. All the outlined gives reason to recognize the usefulness of digital marketing in a competitive market. The presented study also determined the positive attitude of future specialists in the field of management toward Internet marketing. For instance, the importance of websites was rated at 9 points (on a 10-point scale); video blogging received 7 points at the beginning of the program, and at the end, it increased to 8 points.

In addition, several studies consider Search Engine Optimization, Search Engine Marketing, Content Marketing, Social Media Marketing, Pay-Per-Click Marketing, Affiliate Marketing, and Email Marketing to be among the most critical components of Digital Marketing. Our research group supplemented this list with Website/Blog and Video Blogging as equally significant components that should be considered.

In prospect, studies in the field of adaptation of foreign innovations to Ukrainian Internet marketing should be conducted, where priority should belong to the practical skills and abilities of modern specialists familiar with and working with new online marketing tools.

7 Conclusions

The obtained research results have shown that the use of practical achievements of studying foreign experience in advertising and professional education in the training of specialists is positively perceived by the education seekers in the

training course framework. Both the teaching staff and students are ready to improve their level of digital literacy constantly, to use high technologies in the educational process.

Digital technologies as a tool for increasing the effectiveness of the theory and methodology of professional education are effective and necessary in the conditions of the successful existence of a higher school. The preparation of learning technologies, the proper introduction of innovations, and the support of administration and management are necessary to successfully implement such programs. The process of integration of digital technologies in professional education should be straightforward, planned and permanent. It is precisely such projects that ensure success and advantages in the market of educational services for the university and demand in the labor market of future specialists.

In the case of introducing a digital marketing experience, the most important thing is the ability to use the entire set of tools and establish a connection with the audience of consumers. One should possess the basics of online work to attract customers; after all, to use digital marketing effectively, one should be able to develop an effective platform. The experiment participants assessed the cost of training and the relevance of specific skills in the field of blogging and creating video blogs at 8-9 points (on a 10-point scale). Based on the results of the surveys, it can be concluded that integrating all advertising and marketing systems with the digital platform system is of particular importance. The increase at the end of the project of respondents interested in studying Internet marketing (in total, by 9%) shows the trend towards digitization and active, practical implementation of digital marketing in modern business sectors.

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